

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Srinivas Nagar, Mukka– 574 146, Surathkal, Mangaluru, Phone: 0824-2477456

(Private University Established by Karnataka Govt. ACT No.42 of 2013.)

(Recognized by AICTE New Delhi/ UGC New Delhi/Govt. of Karnataka)

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Administrative Office: G.H.S Road, Mangaluru-575001, Phone 0824-2425966

Date: 20/06/2021

Notification

In pursuance of resolution passed by the Board of Management in its Sixteenth meeting held on -19/06/21 at Chancellor's office and agenda item no 8 thereon, it is hereby informed to all the concerned that the faculty posts have been sanctioned for the academic year 2017 -18 for all streams are as below.

Si No	Particulars	Post Sanctioned
1	Faculty post	297

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE